

Effect of Yogic Diet on Physiological Variable of Collegiate Students

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to find out the effect of yogic diet on physiological variable among obese collegiate male students. To achieve the purpose of this study, twenty obese collegiate students were selected from Rajarshi Chhatrapati Shahu College Kolhapur. Obesity of the subjects were determined through a person's body mass index measurement. For this study students with 30 kg/m² and above of Body Mass Index is considered as obese. The subjects were randomly divided into two groups and each group contained ten subjects. One experimental group and other control group. Experimental group underwent yogic diet; control group did not part any activity. The investigator got individual consent from each subject. The yogic diet on selected physiological variable. Pre tests were conducted for all the subjects on physiological variable such as Vital capacity. The experimental groups yogic diet for a period of twelve weeks. The post tests were conducted on the above said dependent variables after a period of twelve weeks in the respective treatments. The difference between the initial and final means on data was considered as the effect of respective treatments. To find out the statistical significance t-test was employed. In all cases 0.05 level was fixed to test the significance. It was concluded that yogic diet program significantly improved physiological variable such as Vital capacity among obese collegiate students.

Keywords: Obese Male Collegiate Students, Physiological Variable & Vital capacity

Material and Method

To purpose of this study, 20 obese collegiate male students were selected from Rajarshi Chhatrapati Shahu College Kolhapur. The 20 obese samples would be divided into two groups of 10 each. Group I acted as experimental group and group II acted as control group. Group I underwent yogic diet; group II control group was under the supervision of the investigator and did not undergo any special training during the experimental period of twelve weeks. Pre-test and post-tests would be conducted. Treatment would be given for twelve weeks. It would be found out

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finally the effects of yogic diet on the obese collegiate male students in scientific method. The research scholar reviewed various scientific literature pertaining to the yoga diet on selected physiological variable. The selected test was measured by the units for testing the hypotheses. Vital Capacity was measured the largest quantity of air (inspiration and expiration).

Yogic Diet Program

Water Intake	: Should be 8 glasses per day
Bed Time Morning	: Water/green tea
Morning Break Fast	: Vegetable Soup 1. Idli 2 with Roasted Bengal grams Chutny 2. Dosai 3 without oil roasted Bengal Grams chutney 3. Chapatti without oil 2 with potato/channa 4. Bread 4 slice with Jame 1 tsp / egg 1 (boiled) 5. Uppuma 1 cup with chutney
Mid-Morning	: Lime Juice 1 cup with 1 tsp with sugar
Lunch	: Rice (75 g) – 1 bowl Sambar ½ cup – 1 cup Rasam ½ cup Curd ½ cup Veg 1 ½ cup / Greens ½ Cup
Evening Snakes	: Fruits 2 /Banana 2
Dinner	: Rice 50 g (3/4 bowl) Sambar, Rasam/Curd
Bed time Night	: Water

Collection of Data

Group I acted as experimental group and group II acted as control group. Group I underwent yogic diet; group II control group was under the supervision of the investigator and did not undergo any special training during the experimental period of twelve weeks. Pre-test and post-tests would be implemented for collection data. To find out the result statistical significance t-test was employed. In all cases 0.05 level was fixed to test the significance.

Results:

The data obtained from the experimental groups before and after the experimental period were statistically analyzed with independent ‘t’ test. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 level for all the cases.

Table no. 1
Statistical Analysis of Vital Capacity

Groups		N	Mean	SD	't' Value
Experimental Group	Pre-test	10	2055.33	289.03	9.520
	Post-test		2329.33	274.73	
Control Group	Pre-test	10	2021.33	182.36	
	Post-test		2023.33	182.58	

The pre and post-test mean values of experimental and control groups on Vital Capacity are graphically presented in below figure.

Figure no. 1

Discussion

The t-test of vital capacity indicated that experimental group compared with control group was significantly improved the vital capacity. It may be due to the effect of yogic diet program. The result of the study supported by the findings of Dhanraj which states that there is a significant reduction in Vital Capacity due to regular training.

During strenuous exercise the size of the chest cavity and alveolus was increased due to the muscles involved in the inspiration and expiration. The tidal volume is increased several times over its resting value. This change in tidal volume is brought about primarily from a decrease in the inspiratory reserved volume although the expiratory reserve volume is also lowered somewhat. Blood flow increases in the capillaries of the lungs during exercise, the available gas volume space is somewhat increased, and as a result there is generally a slight increase in Vital Capacity as well as in the total lung capacity. During exercise residual volume and functional residual capacity will both be slightly increased over the resting capacity will both be slightly increased over the resting values. Although it has been demonstrated that the body size is proportional to Vital Capacity and total lung capacity with the exception of tidal volume, Lamy G. Shaver (1982).

Conclusion

The experimental group provide yogic diet program was significantly improved the vital capacity than compared to the control group of obese collegiate male students due to the effective yogic diet program.

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